

Appendix S3: Alpha diversity, abundance, biomass model plots: Multi panel trend plots, beta coefficient plots and nested model summaries

Fractal sampling design reveals climate and scale effects on rainforest bird communities in central Africa

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Appendix S3 compiles model-based plots that visualize the effects of climatic variables on diversity, abundance, and biomass. These include (1) multi-panel trend plots depicting predicted relationships between climatic gradients (mean annual precipitation, MAP; mean annual temperature, MAT; precipitation seasonality, PS; and temperature seasonality, TS) and community metrics across triad levels, and (2) standardized beta-coefficient plots summarizing the direction, magnitude, and uncertainty of model estimates across spatial scales.

All plots are derived from parameter estimates and predicted values from single-covariate models fitted separately for each triad level and response variable (Phase 1). Blue shading represents 95% confidence intervals (CI). Because single-covariate effects are fully summarized by the trend and standardized beta-coefficient plots—which jointly report effect direction, magnitude, uncertainty, and statistical significance—full coefficient tables for single-covariate models across triad scenarios are not shown to avoid redundancy.

For models fitted using generalized additive models (GAMs) or generalized additive mixed-effects models (GAMMs), confidence intervals are represented as smooth envelopes rather than discrete error bars, reflecting the continuous nature of the fitted spline functions. In contrast, linear and mixed-effects models display confidence intervals as point estimates with symmetric error bars. When model uncertainty was exceptionally high (e.g., for some first-triad estimates), confidence intervals were omitted for clarity and explicitly noted in the corresponding figure captions.

Trend plots: These sets of plots show model-based predictions of size-standardized Hill-number alpha diversity ($q=0,1,2$; $q = 0, 1, 2$; $q=0,1,2$) estimated at the alpha-plot level across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios) corresponding to different effective spatial grains. Solid lines represent predicted values from single-covariate models (phase 1), and shaded bands indicate 95% confidence intervals around the predictions. Hill numbers were standardized to a common sample size to ensure comparability among plots. Labels indicating “significant”

denote predictors whose effects were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) in the corresponding single-covariate models (phase 1) and do not imply significance at individual data points.

FIGURE S1 Multi panel trend plots showing the predicted effects of MAP on alpha diversity (size-standardized Hill-numbers) across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios).

FIGURE S2 Multi panel trend plots showing the predicted effects of MAT on alpha diversity (size-standardized Hill-numbers) across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios).

FIGURE S3 Multi panel trend plots showing the predicted effects of PS on alpha diversity (size-standardized Hill-numbers) across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios).

FIGURE S4 Multi panel trend plots showing the predicted effects of TS on alpha diversity (size-standardized Hill-numbers) across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios).

FIGURE S5 Multi panel trend plots showing the predicted effects of MAP on aggregated community abundance (ACA) (left panel) and aggregated community biomass (ACB) (right panel) across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios).

FIGURE S6 Multi panel trend plots showing the predicted effects of MAT on aggregated community abundance (ACA) (left panel) and aggregated community biomass (ACB) (right panel) across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios).

Notes: CI not plotted for first triad due to very high uncertainty in model estimates.

FIGURE S7 Multi panel trend plots showing the predicted effects of PS on aggregated community abundance (ACA) (left panel) and aggregated community biomass (ACB) (right panel) across sampling scenarios (triad scenarios).

FIGURE S8 Panel trend plot showing the predicted effects of MAT and TS on alpha diversity (size-standardized Hill-numbers) (full sampling scenario, n= 144 point counts). Upper panel (A) corresponds to Mean annual temperature, while lower panel (B) corresponds to Temperature seasonality

FIGURE S9 Beta coefficients plots across different sampling scenarios for the effects of MAP on alpha diversity Hill numbers.

FIGURE S10 Beta coefficients plots across different sampling scenarios for the effects of MAP on aggregated community abundance (ACA) and aggregated community biomass (ACB).

FIGURE S11 Beta coefficients plots across different sampling scenarios for the effects of PS on aggregated community abundance (ACA) and aggregated community biomass (ACB).

Table S1: Single-covariate models for abundance and biomass (full sampling scenario)

Results of single-covariate generalized linear mixed-effects models testing climatic effects on community-level abundance and biomass. Abundance was modelled using negative binomial GLMMs, and biomass using Gamma GLMMs with a log link. Reported values correspond to slope (β) estimates for focal predictors only; intercepts are omitted for clarity. Statistically significant effects ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Response	Predictor	Model type	β estimate	Std. error	z-value	p-value
Abundance	Mean annual precipitation (MAP)	Negative binomial GLMM	-0.0649	0.0208	-3.12	0.0018
Abundance	Mean annual temperature (MAT)	Negative binomial GLMM	-0.023	0.036	-0.62	0.534
Abundance	Precipitation seasonality (PS)	Negative binomial GLMM	-0.0409	0.0320	-1.28	0.201
Abundance	Temperature seasonality (TS)	Negative binomial GLMM	-0.0752	0.0190	-3.93	< 0.001
Biomass	Mean annual	Gamma GLMM (log link)	-0.0020	0.0486	-0.04	0.967

	precipitation (MAP)					
Biomass	Mean annual temperature (MAT)	Gamma GLMM (log link)	0.054	0.043	1.25	0.213
Biomass	Precipitation seasonality (PS)	Gamma GLMM (log link)	-0.0923	0.0420	-2.20	0.0278
Biomass	Temperature seasonality (TS)	Gamma GLMM (log link)	-0.0466	0.0420	-1.11	0.269

Nested models

Full outputs of nested models evaluating the relative importance of mean and seasonality components within precipitation (MAP + PS) and temperature (MAT + TS) axes for size-standardized Hill-number alpha diversity ($q = 0, 1, 2$). Model performance is summarized using AIC, marginal R^2 (variance explained by fixed effects), and likelihood-ratio test p-values (LRT_p) for the nested comparison. Fixed-effect coefficients are reported below; statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Table S2: Model performance and variance explained (marginal R^2) (full sampling scenario).

Climatic axis	Hill number (q)	Model	AIC	Marginal R^2	LRT_p
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 0	MAP + PS	856.1895	7.6%	0.07308958
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 1	MAP + PS	887.7223	20.8%	0.028279
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 2	MAP + PS	942.9989	22.8%	0.0104189
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 0	MAT + TS	853.95490	9.1%	0.02391
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 1	MAT + TS	886.69480	21.5%	0.01692
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 2	MAT + TS	941.90620	23.3%	0.00603

Table S3: Fixed-effect coefficients for nested models (full sampling scenario).

Climatic axis	Hill number (q)	Term	β	SE	Test statistic	p-value
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 0	MAP_z	-0.7483	0.3971	-1.8841	0.133
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 0	PS_z	1.1488	0.3971	2.8926	0.0444
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 1	MAP_z	-0.212	0.5818	-0.3645	0.734
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 1	PS_z	2.5825	0.5818	4.4384	0.0114
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 2	MAP_z	-0.0216	0.5608	-0.0385	0.971
Precipitation (MAP + PS)	q = 2	PS_z	3.3266	0.5608	5.9321	0.00406
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 0	MAT_z	-1.53087	0.41517	-3.68732	0.00032
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 0	TS_z	0.34153	0.41517	0.82262	0.41208
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 1	MAT_z	-2.74839	0.51966	-5.28883	0.00600
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 1	TS_z	1.99230	0.51942	3.83559	0.01797
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 2	MAT_z	-3.38188	0.56345	-6.00211	0.00000
Temperature (MAT + TS)	q = 2	TS_z	2.82263	0.56345	5.00955	0.00000

Note: Marginal R^2 represents variance explained by fixed effects (climatic predictors) only. Alpha diversity was quantified using size-standardized Hill numbers at the alpha-plot level.

Nested climatic models for abundance and biomass

Full results of nested models evaluating the relative importance of mean and seasonality components of precipitation (MAP + PS) and temperature (MAT+ TS) for community-level bird abundance and biomass. Abundance was modelled using negative binomial GLMMs and biomass using Gamma GLMMs. Variance explained is reported as marginal R^2 (fixed effects only). Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Table S4 Model performance and variance explained for nested abundance and biomass models (full sampling scenario).

Response	Climatic axis	Model	AIC	Marginal R^2	LRT_p
Abundance	MAT+ TS)	MAT+ TS	1149.228	8.38%	0.015

Biomass	Temperature (TempGrad + TS)	MAT+ TS	2821.429	3.17%	0.106
Abundance	Precipitation (MAP + PS)	MAP + PS	1149.314	8.33%	0.0157
Biomass	Precipitation (MAP + PS)	MAP + PS	2821.385	3.19%	0.1034

Table S5 Fixed-effect coefficients for nested abundance and biomass models (full sampling scenario).

Response	Climatic axis	Term	β estimate	SE	Test statistic	p-value
Abundance	Temperature	MAT_z	0.537	1.154	$z = 0.47$	0.643
Abundance	Temperature	TS_z	-3.979	1.154	$z = -3.45$	0.0008
Biomass	Temperature	MAT_z	692.472	382.308	$z = 1.81$	0.0722
Biomass	Temperature	TS_z	-700.764	382.197	$z = -1.83$	0.0688
Abundance	Precipitation	MAP_z	-3.095	1.047	$z = -2.96$	0.0036
Abundance	Precipitation	PS_z	-0.159	0.082	$z = -1.93$	0.0558
Biomass	Precipitation	MAP_z	-33.402	346.937	$z = -0.10$	0.9234
Biomass	Precipitation	PS_z	-59.098	27.318	$z = -2.16$	0.0322

Note: Marginal R^2 represents variance explained by climatic predictors only. Intercepts are omitted for clarity. Abundance was modelled using negative binomial GLMMs and biomass using Gamma GLMMs.

Nested models sampling scenarios

Full results of (size-standardized) Hill-number alpha diversity models fitted separately for the third, second, and first triad sampling scenarios. For each sampling scenario (triad level), results are presented as (i) model performance summaries including variance explained (marginal R^2) and (ii) fixed-effect coefficient estimates. Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Full third-triad alpha diversity model results

This appendix reports the complete results of (size-standardized) Hill-number alpha diversity models fitted for the third-triad sampling scenario only. Models evaluate the relative effects of precipitation (MAP, PS) and temperature (Temp, TS) axes. Variance explained is reported as marginal R^2 (fixed effects only). Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Table S6: Model performance and variance explained (third triad).

Climatic axis	Hill number (q)	Model	AIC	Marginal R^2	LRT_p
Precipitation	q = 0	MAP + PS	653.57	5.85%	0.124
Precipitation	q = 1	MAP + PS	675.53	22.56%	0.041
Precipitation	q = 2	MAP + PS	716.51	25.06%	0.020

Temperature	q = 0	Temp + TS	652.07	7.16%	0.059
Temperature	q = 1	Temp + TS	674.81	23.22%	0.028
Temperature	q = 2	Temp + TS	715.59	25.67%	0.013

Table S7: Fixed-effect coefficients for third-triad alpha diversity models.

Climatic axis	Hill number (q)	Term	β	SE	Statistic	p-value
Precipitation	q = 0	MAP_z	-0.567	0.459	z = -1.24	0.219
Precipitation	q = 0	PS_z	1.093	0.459	z = 2.38	0.019
Precipitation	q = 1	MAP_z	0.019	0.702	z = 0.03	0.980
Precipitation	q = 1	PS_z	2.782	0.702	z = 3.96	0.017
Precipitation	q = 2	MAP_z	0.200	0.738	z = 0.27	0.800
Precipitation	q = 2	PS_z	3.598	0.738	z = 4.87	0.008
Temperature	q = 0	Temp_z	-1.415	0.498	z = -2.84	0.005
Temperature	q = 0	TS_z	0.395	0.498	z = 0.79	0.430
Temperature	q = 1	Temp_z	-2.891	0.674	z = -4.29	0.013
Temperature	q = 1	TS_z	2.284	0.673	z = 3.39	0.026
Temperature	q = 2	Temp_z	-3.613	0.714	z = -5.06	0.007
Temperature	q = 2	TS_z	3.180	0.714	z = 4.45	0.011

Note: Marginal R^2 represents variance explained by climatic predictors only. Alpha diversity was quantified using size-standardized Hill numbers. Intercepts are omitted for clarity.

Nested models for alpha diversity – Second triad

This appendix reports the full results of nested mixed-effects models fitted to size-standardized (rarefied) Hill-number alpha diversity for the second triad sampling scenario. Models evaluate the relative contributions of precipitation (MAP, PS) and temperature (MAT, TS) axes. Variance explained is reported as marginal R^2 (fixed effects only). Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Table S8: Model performance and variance explained (second triad).

Climatic axis	Hill number (q)	Model	AIC	Marginal R^2	LRT p-value
Precipitation	q = 0	MAP + PS	224.22	1.11%	0.822
Precipitation	q = 1	MAP + PS	240.76	22.37%	0.044
Precipitation	q = 2	MAP + PS	250.50	26.63%	0.051
Temperature	q = 0	MAT + TS	224.33	0.81%	0.867
Temperature	q = 1	MAT + TS	240.77	22.34%	0.044
Temperature	q = 2	MAT + TS	249.95	27.76%	0.039

Table S9: Fixed-effect coefficients for nested alpha diversity models (second triad).

Climatic axis	Hill number (q)	Term	β	SE	t-value	p-value
Precipitation	q = 0	MAP_z	-0.27	0.77	-0.34	0.733
Precipitation	q = 0	PS_z	0.43	0.77	0.56	0.580
Precipitation	q = 1	MAP_z	0.13	0.99	0.14	0.893
Precipitation	q = 1	PS_z	3.10	0.99	3.14	0.003
Precipitation	q = 2	MAP_z	-0.16	1.13	-0.14	0.887
Precipitation	q = 2	PS_z	4.02	1.13	3.56	0.001
Temperature	q = 0	MAT_z	-0.44	0.84	-0.52	0.608
Temperature	q = 0	TS_z	0.07	0.84	0.09	0.932
Temperature	q = 1	MAT_z	-3.08	1.07	-2.87	0.0069
Temperature	q = 1	TS_z	2.59	1.07	2.41	0.021
Temperature	q = 2	MAT_z	-4.17	1.22	-3.42	0.0016
Temperature	q = 2	TS_z	3.19	1.22	2.61	0.013

Note: Marginal R^2 represents variance explained by climatic predictors only. Alpha diversity was quantified using size-standardized Hill numbers. Intercepts are omitted for clarity.

Nested models for alpha diversity – First triad

This appendix reports the full results of nested mixed-effects models fitted to size-standardized (rarefied) Hill-number alpha diversity for the first triad sampling scenario. Models evaluate the relative contributions of precipitation (MAP, PS) and temperature (MAT, TS) axes. Variance explained is reported as marginal R^2 (fixed effects only). Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Table S10. Model performance and variance explained (first triad).

Climatic axis	Hill number (q)	Model	AIC	Marginal R^2	LRT p-value
Precipitation	q = 0	MAP + PS	83.01	5.15%	0.747
Precipitation	q = 1	MAP + PS	90.54	23.60%	0.224
Precipitation	q = 2	MAP + PS	92.77	19.46%	0.303
Temperature	q = 0	MAT + TS	83.21	3.41%	0.826
Temperature	q = 1	MAT + TS	90.78	21.91%	0.253
Temperature	q = 2	MAT + TS	92.80	19.34%	0.308

Table S11. Fixed-effect coefficients for nested alpha diversity models (first triad).

Climatic axis	Hill number (q)	Term	β	SE	Statistic	p-value
Precipitation	q = 0	MAP_z	-0.501	1.415	t = -0.35	0.730
Precipitation	q = 0	PS_z	1.023	1.415	t = 0.72	0.484
Precipitation	q = 1	MAP_z	0.401	1.936	t = 0.21	0.840

Precipitation	q = 1	PS_z	3.480	1.936	t = 1.80	0.098
Precipitation	q = 2	MAP_z	0.399	2.125	t = 0.19	0.854
Precipitation	q = 2	PS_z	3.375	2.125	t = 1.59	0.138
Temperature	q = 0	MAT_z	-0.954	1.544	t = -0.62	0.548
Temperature	q = 0	TS_z	0.258	1.544	t = 0.17	0.869
Temperature	q = 1	MAT_z	-3.265	2.117	t = -1.54	0.149
Temperature	q = 1	TS_z	2.929	2.117	t = 1.38	0.193
Temperature	q = 2	MAT_z	-3.331	2.295	t = -1.45	0.172
Temperature	q = 2	TS_z	2.856	2.295	t = 1.24	0.241

Note: Marginal R² represents variance explained by climatic predictors only. Alpha diversity was quantified using size-standardized Hill numbers. Intercepts are omitted for clarity.

Third-triad nested models for abundance and biomass

This appendix reports nested mixed-effects model results for the third-triad sampling scenario, evaluating climatic axes for aggregated community abundance (ACA; Total Max Abundance) and aggregated community biomass (ACB; Total Biomass). Models were fitted separately for the precipitation axis (MAP and precipitation seasonality, PS) and the temperature axis (mean annual temperature, MAT, and temperature seasonality, TS). Variance explained is reported as marginal R² (fixed effects only). Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Table S12. Model performance and variance explained (third triad).

Climatic axis	Response	Model	AIC	Marginal R ²	LRT p-value	Singular fit
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAP + PS (std)	883.7805	0.0861493	0.02833269	True
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAP + PS (std)	2121.7272	0.03773862	0.13393583	True
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAT + TS (std)	883.8031	0.08587397	0.02865508	True
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAT + TS (std)	2121.5088	0.03975201	0.120082	True

Table S13 Fixed-effect coefficients (third triad).

Climatic axis	Response	Term	β	SE	Statistic	df	p-value	CI low	CI high
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	(Intercept)	51.481481	1.650172	31.1976544	2.999951	7.236932e-05	46.229851	56.733111
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAP_z	-2.89195	1.323133	-2.1856839	105.005802	0.03106037	-5.515477	-0.2684239

Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	PS_z	- 2.7220 88	1.323 124	- 2.057 3189	105.0 00923	0.0421 3352	- 5.3455 98	- 0.09857 774
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	(Intercept)	8254.0 72963	610.2 82547	13.52 50025	2.999 969	0.0008 74178	6311.8 70286	10196.2 8
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAP_z	85.501 258	405.8 75687	0.210 6587	105.0 03991	0.83356 18	- 719.27 4898	890.277 4
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	PS_z	- 831.42 3422	405.8 7144	- 2.048 4896	105.0 00633	0.0430 0656	- 1636.1 91457	- 26.6553 9
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	(Intercept)	51.481 481	1.601 335	32.14 911	2.992 405	6.7439 23e-05	46.377 995	56.5849 68
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAT_z (Temp_z)	1.5971 93	1.449 228	1.102 099	105.2 57122	0.27293 21	- 1.2762 76	4.47066 2
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	TS_z	- 4.5803 33	1.448 854	- 3.161 35	105.0 41692	0.0020 52641	- 7.4531 29	- 1.70753 7
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	(Intercept)	8254.0 72963	618.6 31127	13.34 2479	2.994 982	0.0009 177948	6283.4 45042	10224.7 00884
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAT_z (Temp_z)	856.63 7782	443.5 96842	1.931 118	105.1 62466	0.05616 066	- 22.916 973	1736.19 2537
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	TS_z	- 693.43 2295	443.3 95634	- 1.563 913	105.0 25977	0.12084 62	- 1572.6 01395	185.736 805

Note: ACA and ACB were analysed using standardized climatic predictors (z-scores). Singular fits are indicated as reported by the model output.

Second-triad nested models for abundance and biomass

This appendix reports nested mixed-effects model results for the second-triad sampling scenario, evaluating climatic axes for aggregated community abundance (ACA) and aggregated community biomass (ACB). Models were fitted separately for precipitation (MAP and PS) and temperature (MAT and TS) axes. Marginal R^2 represents variance explained by fixed effects. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Table S14 Model performance and variance explained (second triad).

Climatic axis	Response	Model	AIC	Marginal R^2	LRT p-value	Singular fit
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAP + PS (std)	317.2377	0.1447	0.1141	True

Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAP + PS (std)	725.9687	0.0681	0.4177	False
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAT + TS (std)	317.0753	0.1487	0.1052	True
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAT + TS (std)	725.2488	0.0885	0.2914	False

Table S15 Fixed-effect coefficients (second triad).

Climatic axis	Response	Term	β	SE	Statistic	df	p-value	CI low	CI high
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	(Intercept)	54.666667	2.906256	18.81	2.999887	0.0003281	45.417466	63.915868
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAP_z	-2.601646	2.844606	-0.9146	33.0043	0.3670412	-8.389012	3.185720
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	PS_z	-6.089620	2.844599	-2.1408	33.0006	0.0397730	-11.876997	-0.302244
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	(Intercept)	9607.316944	941.213443	10.21	1.659663	0.0171194	4647.763375	14566.870514
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAP_z	477.944492	904.568878	0.5284	3.775053	0.6267712	-2093.677285	3049.566269
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	PS_z	-1291.577521	904.597874	-1.4278	3.772047	0.2306283	-3864.150152	1280.995110
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	(Intercept)	54.666667	2.902869	18.83	2.987766	0.0003351	45.407004	63.926329
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAT_z	5.490061	3.090070	1.7767	33.10085	0.0848134	-0.796006	11.776128
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	TS_z	-7.090282	3.089923	-2.2946	33.03102	0.0282438	-13.376554	-0.804011
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	(Intercept)	9607.316944	876.424732	10.96	2.981023	0.0016725	6808.070417	12406.563472
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAT_z	1656.040459	892.128349	1.8563	33.08173	0.0723391	-158.837987	3470.918904
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	TS_z	-733.384784	892.045222	-0.8221	33.01774	0.4168958	-2548.227402	1081.457834

Note: Climatic predictors were standardized (z-scores). Singular fits are indicated as reported by the model diagnostics.

First-triad nested models for abundance and biomass

Reports of nested mixed-effects model results for the first-triad sampling scenario, evaluating climatic axes for aggregated community abundance (ACA) and aggregated community biomass (ACB). Models were fitted separately for precipitation (MAP and PS) and temperature (MAT and TS) axes. Marginal R^2 represents variance explained by fixed effects. Statistically significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are shown in bold.

Table S16 Model performance and variance explained (first triad).

Climatic axis	Response	Model	AIC	Marginal R^2	LRT p-value	Singular fit
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAP + PS (std)	111.1147	0.0922	0.5861	True
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAP + PS (std)	249.2384	0.0002	0.9988	True
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAT + TS (std)	111.1955	0.0856	0.6102	True
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAT + TS (std)	249.2236	0.0016	0.9914	True

Table S17 Fixed-effect coefficients (first triad).

Climatic axis	Response	Term	β	SE	Statistic	df	p-value	CI low	CI high
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	(Intercept)	53.0	4.34	12.21	12	0.0000	43.54	62.46
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAP_z	-2.3532	4.56	-0.52	12	0.6155	-12.3	7.59
Precipitation	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	PS_z	-3.9221	4.56	-0.86	12	0.4070	-13.87	6.02
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	(Intercept)	9515.3542	1574.8	6.04	3	0.0091	4503.47	14527.24
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAP_z	-65.6548	1376.47	-0.048	9	0.9630	-3179.39	3048.08
Precipitation	ACB (TotalBiomass)	PS_z	-9.3007	1376.45	-0.0068	9	0.9948	-3123.05	3104.45
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	(Intercept)	53.0	4.3569	12.1647	12	0.0000	44.4607	61.5393

Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	MAT_z	2.651	4.8647	0.5449	12	0.6102	-6.8837	12.1857
Temperature	ACA (TotalMaxAbundance)	TS_z	-4.8325	4.8647	-0.9934	12	0.6102	-14.3671	4.7022
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	(Intercept)	9515.3542	1575.7164	6.0387	3	0.0091	6427.01	12603.70
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	MAT_z	-131.2528	1460.922	-0.0898	9	0.9914	-2994.61	2732.10
Temperature	ACB (TotalBiomass)	TS_z	177.9218	1461.1836	0.1218	9	0.9914	-2685.95	3041.79

Note: Climatic predictors were standardized (z-scores). Singular fits were common at this spatial grain, reflecting limited replication at the first-triad level.